

smFISH base protocol

Short name: smFISH-base-protocol

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Abstract: smFISH allows the **visualization of individual RNA molecules**. For each target RNA, several short DNA oligonucleotides (probes) are bioinformatically designed and can be fluorescently labelled with different strategies. Using a sufficiently large number of probes (usually between 20 and 100) yields strong local signal enrichment compared to individual non-specifically bound stray probes or autofluorescence. Samples can be imaged with different microscopes (widefield, spinning disc, light sheet), and individual RNAs appear as bright diffraction-limited spots. Interestingly, this protocol can also be expanded to include **tissue clearing, signal amplification, or sequential FISH**. For this, we refer to separate protocols.

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1 Materials

1.1 Reagents

32% Paraformaldehyde aqueous solution, methanol free, EM grade	Electron Microscopy Sciences - 15714
H2O DEPC (Nuclease free water)	Ambion™ - AM9922
10X PBS	Ambion™ - AM9625
PBS++	DPBS Gibco 14040117 Thermofisher
20X SSC	Ambion™ - AM9770
Dextran sulphate	SigmaAldrich - D8906
Formamide	Ambion - AM9342
Triton	SigmaAldrich T8787
IDT TE pH 8.0	Integrated DNA Technologies - 11010205
NEBuffer 3	New England Biolabs - B7003S
70% ethanol molecular grade	SigmaAldrich - 51976
DAPI	SigmaAldrich – M800015
KOH	Honeywell, 06005
Ethanol	VWR, 20821.310
Acetone	Honeywell, 32201
PH paper	422404 Clearline Dutscher

For **standard smFISH**, we usually use ProLong as a mounting medium.

ProLong™ Diamond Antifade Mountant	ThermoFisher - P36970
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1.2 Oligos

- We order all oligos from IDT unless specified otherwise.
- **Indicated prices are only indicative and can differ based on country and institute discounts.**

1.2.1 Primary oligos

We usually buy oPools (IDT) with a synthesis of up to 340 nucleotides. The downsides are the reduced amount (still enough for hundreds of experiments) and the inability to test individual oligos.

1.2.1.1 IDT oPool: small scale without the need for amplification

- Roughly **100 euros for 50 oligos**
 - **Scale 50 pmol/oligo** is enough for a few hundred coverslips
 - Can be **used directly** for FISH without the need for amplification.
- Up to 384 oligos per tube, but it can be **interesting to create oPools for individual genes**. It is not much more expensive and gives more flexibility.
- **Length up to 350 bases** (permits having several overhang sequences)
- Arrives dry, needs to be **diluted and stored in aliquots**:
 - Dilute in 500 µL TE (0.1 µM/oligo)
 - 1 µL is used for 50 µL of hybridization mix (required for one 12 mm coverslip).
 - Recommended are 10 µL aliquots in PCR tubes, which fit into one 50 mL Falcon tube for easy storage.
 - Stored at -20 °C, minimize freeze-thaw cycles (no more than 5).

1.2.1.2 IDT plates

- Roughly **100 euros for 24 oligos**
- **25nmol/oligo**: enough for thousands of experiments
- **Individual oligos**: a custom mix can be created (e.g., to label different parts of the RNA in different colors).
- Length < 60 nts (only one barcode)

1.2.2 Readout oligos

- Ordered in tubes
- **100 nmol** is sufficient for most use.
 - Frozen, 100 μ M.
 - We create working stock (50 μ L) diluted 1:5 in TE (20 μ M final), which we use up to 5 times.
- Note that you can also order these oligos directly labeled. They will be more expensive, but no separate imager oligo is needed. Combining with an imager is also possible, providing a slight signal amplification.
- HPLC purification is optional (but more expensive)

Amount	Purification	~Final volume	~price
100 nmol	No HPLC	400 μ L	20€
100 nmol	HPLC	400 μ L	60€
250 nmol	HPLC	800 μ L	80€

1.2.3 Imaging oligos

- Ordered in tubes
 - 250nmol is sufficient for most applications.
 - Frozen, 100 μ M.
 - Stored at -20 °C in 10 μ L aliquots (PCR tubes).
 - Fluorophores on 3' and 5' are possible.

Amount	Purification	~Final volume	~price
100 nmol	HPLC	50 μ L	180€
250 nmol	HPLC	100 μ L	280€
1 μ mol	HPLC	400 μ L	450€
2 μ mol	HPLC	800 μ L	700€

1.3 Sample supports and buffer volumes

- For **standard smFISH**, we use 12- or 18-mm coverslips (#1.5).
- If several conditions are tested, smFISH can also be performed in **multi-well plates**. We routinely use Ibidi 8- or 18-well plates (ideally with a #1.5 glass bottom, which provides the best smFISH signal).
- For **sequential smFISH**, we use either the FCS2 chamber or Ibidi multi-channel slides (see dedicated protocol for more details).

Volumes for washes and hybridizations

Below, we list suggested volumes for washes and hybridizations for different sample supports. The indicated volumes are for **one wash/hybridization per sample or well**.

Support	Wash		Hybridization
	Volume	Support	
12 mm cover slip	1 mL	24 well plate	50 μ L
18 mm cover slip	1 mL	12 well plate	75 μ L
40 mm cover slip	5 mL	50 mm petri dish	400 μ L
Ibidi 8-well	250 μ L	Directly in well	100 μ L
Ibidi 18-well	150 μ L	Directly in well	50 μ L
96 well plate	200 μ L	Directly in well	50 μ L
Ibidi 6 channel slide	500 μ L	Directly in channel	60 μ L

1.4 Buffers

1.4.1 Handling of formamide, PFA, ethylene carbonate

- **Formamide, PFA:** toxic, so use precautions (gloves, fume hood).
- **Ethylene carbonate**
 - Solid, to liquefy heat to 50°C.
 - Pipette with 1000 µL pipettes (with a Pipette Boy it tends to solidify quickly)

1.4.2 Filtering of stock solutions

- We sterile filter all buffers (glucose, Dextran) with a 0.22 µm syringe

1.4.3 Wash and DAPI staining buffers

Always prepared fresh; can be stored for one day at 4°C.

- **Wash buffer I:** 2X SSC
- **Wash buffer II:** 2X SSC, 20% formamide
- **DAPI staining buffer**
 - a. DAPI 1:1000: 2 µL in 2 mL.
 - b. Dilution 2: 1:2000 in PBS, e.g., 0.5 µL in 1 mL PBS.

1.4.4 Hybridization buffer (primary and secondary hybridization)

We create a **stock solution** that can be prepared in large quantities and frozen in aliquots.

Reagent	Amount	Final
Formamide	2 mL	20%
20X SSC	1 mL	2X
Dextran 40%	2.5 mL	10%
H2O DEPC	4.5 mL	

- **We use a 40% Dextran stock solution**
 - Hard to dissolve (easier at 37°C)
 - Hard to filter
- **Preparation**
 1. 2.5 mL Dextran 40% solution
 2. Add 2 mL formamide, 1 mL 20X SSC
 3. Add water to the final volume of 10 mL.
 4. Aliquot (e.g., 0.5 mL) and store @ -20°C.

The **final hybridization buffer** is prepared fresh by adding 0.1% Triton to increase probe penetration.

2 Methods

2.1 Day 0: hybridization buffer stock and clean coverslips

These steps can be performed before the actual smFISH experiments to create stock and gain time.

2.1.1 Hybridization buffer

Hybridization buffer can be prepared and stored in frozen aliquots (see above).

2.1.2 Clean coverslips

We usually clean coverslips in larger batches to remove dust particles.

1. Wash coverslips 3X with 70% ethanol, then acetone, then water.
2. Place the coverslips in 1M KOH 1M in a Becher. Sonicate during 1h.
3. Rinse the coverslips multiple times in water until neutral pH (measured with PH paper).

🔔 **STORAGE in sterile water for several months.**

2.2 Day 1: fixation, ethanol permeabilization

⚠️ **CRITICAL:** RNA is sensitive – work with gloves and clean the bench carefully.

⚠️ **CRITICAL:** Put 70% Ethanol for a few hours @ -20°C before using it.

1. Thaw the 4% PFA solution and ensure no precipitates are visible (in this case, vortex and heat briefly to 37°C).
2. Wash each sample well with 2 mL of 1X DPBS++.
3. Remove PBS++.
4. Add 1 mL of 4% PFA for each well.
5. Incubate 20 min @ RT.
6. Wash 2X with 2 mL 1X PBS++.
7. Remove PBS++.
8. Add 2 mL of 70% ethanol. Make sure the coverslip does not float.
9. Seal with Parafilm. Leave O/N @ -20°C.

🔔 **PAUSE STEP:** Samples can be stored @ -20°C for several weeks.

2.3 Day 2: hybridize primary oligos

2.3.1 Buffer preparation

For the required buffer volumes, refer to the table above.

- **Wash buffer I (2X SSC):** 5 washes per sample
- **Wash buffer II (2X SSC, 20% formamide):** 5 washes per sample
- **Hybridization buffer:** 1 incubation per sample

10. 🔔 **Wash buffers** are prepared for both days and are stored at 4°C.

1. Prepare the hybridization buffer

- a. Heat the **hybridization buffer** to 90°C for 5 min (to fully dissolve dextran). Let cool to RT.
- b. Add **10% Triton** for a final concentration of **0.1%**.
- c. Add **primary probes**: oPool (IDT, 50 pmol): 1:50 dilution.
- d. **VORTEX** and centrifuge.

2.3.2 Hybridization

⚠️ **CRITICAL:** Ensure that the coverslip does not float during the washing steps.

1. Aspirate the 70% Ethanol.
2. Wash **twice** with 1 mL **wash buffer I**: incubate @ RT for 10 minutes.
3. Wash **once** with 1 mL **wash buffer II**: incubate @ RT for 10 minutes.
4. For **coverslips**, create a **humidified hybridization chamber**
 - a. We use a 100 mL culture dish with a lid lined with wet paper.
 - b. Place parafilm at the bottom.
 - c. Dispense the **hybridization buffer**.
 - d. Place coverslips with cells facing downward on the hybridization buffer.
 - e. Close with a lid, and seal with Parafilm.
 - f. Cover the humidified chamber with the tissue culture lid and seal it with Parafilm.
5. For **multi-well supports**:
 - a. Add hybridization buffer directly to the well.
6. Incubate at 37°C, O/N, protected from light

2.4 Day 3: Hybridization of readout oligos, sample mounting

2.4.1 Preparation

1. Preheat **wash buffer I** and **II** to 37°C.
 2. Prepare the readout working solution.
- Note:** directly labeled readout oligos can be used to amplify the signal.

Reagent	Volume
Readout (Stock 20µM)	2 µL
Imager (Stock 100 µM)	0.5 µL
10X NEB3	1 µL
H2O	6.5 µL
TOTAL	10 µL

3. Prepare the **hybridization buffer**.
 - a. Heat the hybridization buffer to 90°C for 5 min (to fully dissolve dextran). Let cool to RT.
 - b. Add **10% Triton** for a final concentration of **0.1%**.
 - c. Add readout working solution as a 1:50 dilution.
 - d. VORTEX and centrifuge

2.4.2 Hybridization

4. For **coverslips**:
 - a. Preheat the container used for washes (e.g., a 12-well plate) to 37°C.
 - b. Add the appropriate amount of **wash buffer II** to an unused well.
 - c. Transfer the coverslip to a new 12-well plate with the cells facing UPWARD!
5. For **multi-well supports**: aspirate the hybridization buffer.
6. Wash **twice** with **wash buffer II** at 37°C for more than 30 minutes without shaking.
7. Hybridize secondary probes as described for primary probes.
8. Incubate at 37°C for 1 h in the dark.

2.4.3 Washing, DAPI staining, and mounting

1. Wash samples **twice** with **wash buffer II** at 37°C for 20 min in the dark.
2. Wash **once** with **wash buffer I** at RT for 5 min with shaking.
3. Incubate with DAPI staining buffer for 10 min with shaking.
4. Wash **twice** with **wash buffer I** at RT with shaking.
5. Mount (e.g., Prolong Gold), proceed with imaging.

3 Version history

Version	Date	Modified by	Changes
v1	13.11.2024	Mueller F, Weber C	Submission of autoFISH paper.
v2	1.3.2025	Mueller F, Weber C	Resubmission of autoFISH paper. Improved for clarity.